

220 GHz, 8.5-dBm Saturated Output Power Wideband Power Amplifier in SiGe BiCMOS

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Abstract—This letter presents a broadband *G*-band power amplifier (PA) designed in a 130-nm silicon-germanium (SiGe) bipolar complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor technology. Unlike dual-band matching and staggered tuning techniques to obtain large operation bandwidth (BW), we propose a common broadband amplification stage in this work for its flexibility. In each stage, inductive gain peaking is employed at the base terminal of the common-base (CB) transistor for BW extension. Meanwhile, the correlation between BW, inband gain and gain flatness is studied to determine the practical value of the inductance and AC decoupling capacitance. A current-mirror with thermal runaway protection is placed close to the amplifier in the implementation of each stage. The proposed PA achieves a peak small-signal gain of 27.6 dB over an operation BW from 140 to 238.7 GHz in measurements. The saturated output power, P_{sat} , is 8.5 dBm at 220 GHz with a peak power-added efficiency (PAE) of 2.1%. The 3-dB P_{sat} BW ranges from 150 to 220 GHz with fractional BW of 31.8% in measurements. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the PA demonstrates the largest BW in *G*-band compared to other reported silicon-based PAs to date. Furthermore, the inband gain and output power over BW are easily adjustable based on system requirements due to the flexibility of the common broadband amplification stage.

Index Terms—Bipolar complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (BiCMOS), broadband, *G*-band, millimeter-wave (mm-wave), monolithic microwave integrated circuit (MMIC), output power, power-added efficiency (PAE), power amplifier (PA), silicon-germanium (SiGe), wireless communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

Millimeter-wave (mm-wave) frequency bands offer large available bandwidth (BW) for high-data-rate wireless communications, such as beyond-5G and 6G systems. In order to make full use of the BW with the smallest possible area and power consumption, broadband systems are often required. Power amplifiers (PAs) are critical components in these systems to provide adequate gain and output power over the desired BW. For mm-wave frequencies, the silicon-based and III-V semiconductor processes are two candidates to implement PAs. The silicon-based process takes advantage of easier integration of frontend with the digital circuitry, lower cost of production, and lower power consumption. In addition, recent research demonstrates broadband PAs in silicon-based processes such as silicon-germanium (SiGe) bipolar complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (BiCMOS) technologies to operate in *G*-band [1], [2].

Dual-band matching [3], [4] and staggered tuning technique [5], [6] are well-known methods to achieve broadband performance of PAs. They require delicate input, output,

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Fig. 1. Conceptional schematic of the PA with common broadband amplification stages.

and interstage matching networks (MNs), meanwhile taking a risk of imprecise electromagnetic (EM) simulations and fabrication deviation. It is therefore favored to design a common broadband amplification stage. By cascading multiple stages, adequate gain over the desired BW can be obtained.

Based on this concept, a broadband PA is proposed which operates from 140 to 238.7 GHz with eight common broadband amplification stages. Another advantage is that the MNs of the PA can have a low quality factor which is typical for mm-wave technologies.

II. CIRCUIT DESIGN

A conceptional schematic of the broadband PA is shown in Fig. 1. It is composed of eight common broadband amplification stages and the MNs to provide high gain and output power. The common broadband amplification stage consists of cascode transistors, Q_1 and Q_2 , with a base inductor, L_B , at the common-base (CB) transistor, Q_2 , for broadband performance. Each stage is biased by a cascode current-mirror at nodes V_{B1} and V_{B2} with thermal runaway protection as used in [7]. The cascode current-mirror is not shown in Fig. 1 for simplicity. A base capacitor, C_B , is used to provide an AC flow at the base terminal of the CB transistor. R_{LB} and R_E denote the equivalent series resistance (ESR) of L_B and parasitic resistance of Q_1 in the actual process, respectively, to generalize the analysis of broadband performance as followed.

The small-signal equivalent circuit of Q_1 and Q_2 are shown in Fig. 2(a) and (b), respectively. Each transistor is composed of an input resistance, r_π , input capacitance, c_π , base-collector capacitance, c_μ , output resistance, r_o , output capacitance, c_o , and voltage-controlled current source, denoted as $g_m v_\pi$. The base resistance, r_b , is included in the CB transistor equivalent circuit. If c_μ is negligible, the voltage gain can be derived as

$$\frac{v_x}{v_{in}} = \frac{Z_\pi (R_E - g_m Z_o^2) + R_E Z_o}{Z_\pi (R_E + Z_o) + R_E Z_o} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{v_{out}}{v_x} = \frac{g_m Z_o Z_\pi + r_b + R_{LB} + j\omega L_B + \frac{1}{j\omega C_B}}{Z_\pi + r_b + R_{LB} + j\omega L_B + \frac{1}{j\omega C_B}} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2. Small-signal equivalent circuit of (a) Q_1 and (b) Q_2 .

Fig. 3. Simulated small-signal voltage gain. (a) $C_B = 30$ fF and different L_B values. (b) $L_B = 50$ pH and different C_B values.

Z_π and Z_o denote the input and output impedance of the transistor in the equivalent circuit, respectively, given by

$$Z_\pi = \frac{r_\pi}{1 + j\omega C_\pi r_\pi} \quad (3)$$

$$Z_o = \frac{r_o}{1 + j\omega C_o r_o}. \quad (4)$$

Based on (1) and (2), the voltage gain of a cascode stage is plotted in Fig. 3(a) with different values of L_B . Since the voltage gain of common-emitter (CE) and CB transistor decreases with frequency, introducing an LC resonant circuit at the base of the CB transistor provides gain peaking and increases the BW of the cascode stage. Note that the quality factor of L_B is limited in G -band, and

Fig. 4. Layout of the common broadband amplification stage with L_B and C_B .

Fig. 5. MAG and μ -factor of the common broadband amplification stage in postlayout EM cosimulations.

therefore, the value of R_{LB} scales accordingly with L_B in simulations. It is indicated in Fig. 3(a) that larger L_B shifts the zero to lower frequencies and reduces the BW, while an improved inband gain and gain flatness can be achieved. A similar result is obtained with larger C_B as shown in Fig. 3(b), with the simulation results obtained from Keysight ADS shown for comparison. In general, the combination of values of L_B and C_B presents the tradeoff between BW, inband gain, and gain flatness. A common amplification stage can be designed for a specific BW requirement whereas gain flatness should be taken into account if multiple stages are cascaded to achieve a certain inband gain.

The PA is designed in the IHP 130-nm SiGe BiCMOS technology featuring a transistor maximum unity-current-gain cutoff frequency, f_T , of 300 GHz and maximum oscillation frequency, f_{max} , of 450 GHz. The backend offers two thick metal layers, i.e., TM2 and TM1, and five thin metal layers, i.e., M5 to M1. The layout of the common broadband amplification stage is shown in Fig. 4. The stage is designed with grounded coplanar waveguide (GCPW) transmission lines (TLs) with a bottom ground plane on M1. Q_1 and Q_2 are chosen with a multiplier of five, trading off maximum available gain (MAG) and output power. The current-mirror with feedback loop is placed close to the amplification stage to prevent thermal runaway of Q_1 and Q_2 . The transistor interconnect at the base of Q_2 and the 45- μ m line comprise L_B with a simulated inductance value of 45 pH and quality factor of 7.4 at 200 GHz. C_B is implemented as interdigitated metal-oxide-metal (MOM) capacitor on TM2, TM1, and M5 with a value of 30 fF in simulation. Different characteristic impedances at the input and output are matched with a linear tapered section in the MN.

The postlayout EM cosimulation results of the common broadband amplification stage are shown in Fig. 5. The stage achieves an MAG

Fig. 6. Chip photograph of the PA under test.

Fig. 7. Measured (solid) and simulated (dashed) S -parameters of the PA.

between 11 and 11.8 dB from 140 to 230 GHz in simulations with an optimum output impedance of $2.8 + j11.9 \Omega$ at 220 GHz. The saturated output power, P_{sat} , is 6.3 dBm, with an optimum load impedance of $10.7 + j22.1 \Omega$ obtained from load-pull simulations. The interstage matching is designed as a compromise between gain and P_{sat} , and is implemented using a shorted stub followed by a series capacitor and an open stub. A simulated small-signal gain of 7.4 dB and P_{sat} of 5.3 dBm per stage are achieved at 220 GHz, with a maximum power-added efficiency (PAE) of 2.6%. The overall gain and output power of the PA can be further increased with the cost of larger chip size. For the complete PA, both stage and interstage stability are verified using Ohtomo tests in Keysight ADS [8].

III. IMPLEMENTATION AND MEASUREMENT RESULTS

A photograph of the PA is shown in Fig. 6. It occupies an area of $1.6 \times 0.65 \text{ mm}^2$ including all measurement pads, and $1.3 \times 0.37 \text{ mm}^2$ without pads. In measurements the eight single-amplification stages and current-mirrors consume 313.2 and 14.6 mW of DC power with 3.3 V and 2.5 V DC supplies, respectively. The total DC power consumption is 327.8 mW.

The on-wafer measurement environment is set up with a Keysight network analyzer PNA-X, frequency extenders VDI VNAX Mini WR5.1 and WR3.4, and probes i220-S-GSG-BT and i325-S-GSG-BT by FormFactor. The parasitic effects of the measurement pads are de-embedded with an on-wafer through-reflect-line (TRL) structure for small-signal measurements. The measured and simulated S -parameters are presented in Fig. 7. The simulation results are obtained from Keysight ADS with Momentum EM. In measurements, the PA achieves a peak gain of 27.6 dB at 156.8 GHz. The 3-dB BW can be defined in two frequency bands due to the different amplification levels, i.e., from 140 to 173.6 GHz with a maximum gain of 27.6 dB, and from 200 to 238.7 GHz with a maximum gain of 18.4 dB, respectively. The discrepancy at 220 GHz is caused by changing the frequency extenders and probes. It

Fig. 8. (a) Measured (solid) and simulated (dashed) power gain and PAE versus output power. (b) Measured (solid) and simulated (dashed) P_{sat} and $OP_{1\text{dB}}$.

is observed that the measured small-signal gain above 200 GHz decreases significantly compared to simulations. This is suspected to be caused by probe crosstalk in the calibration process [9]. In the lower frequency range, i.e., from 140 to 200 GHz, the measurements align well with simulations, where probe crosstalk is less significant. The gain is above 0 dB from 140 to 250.8 GHz. Measurements at lower frequencies are not performed because of limitations in the available measurement equipment. Nevertheless, according to the postlayout EM cosimulation, the return losses are inadequate at lower frequencies. The PA is unconditionally stable, with μ -factor above 1 in the entire measured band.

Large-signal measurements are carried out using power sweeps of the PNA-X. The measured and simulated linearity sweeps at different frequencies with the corresponding PAE are shown in Fig. 8(a). The proposed PA achieves a measured P_{sat} of 8.5 dBm at 220 GHz with a peak PAE of 2.1%. At 150 GHz, a maximum output power of 8 dBm with a PAE of 1.9% is demonstrated. Since eight common stages are used and each consumes equal DC power, the PAE is lower than in conventional architectures, where the early stages typically draw less current. The measured and simulated P_{sat} and $OP_{1\text{dB}}$ are plotted in Fig. 8(b). The measured minimum P_{sat} over frequencies is 7.2 dBm. The measured 3-dB P_{sat} BW ranges from 150 to 220 GHz. The discrepancy within 2 dB between simulations and measurements are likely caused by limited frequency range of the EM and transistor model for harmonic-balance simulations. A comparison with state-of-the-art PAs using 130-nm SiGe BiCMOS is made in Table I, where the proposed PA demonstrates the highest 3-dB P_{sat} BW of 31.8% to date.

IV. CONCLUSION

This letter proposes and discusses the theory and implementation of a common broadband amplification stage to design PAs in G -band.

TABLE I
COMPARISON WITH STATE-OF-THE-ART PAs USING 130-nm SiGe BiCMOS

Reference	[10]	[11]	[12]	[13]	This work
Frequency (GHz)	220	215	230	220	220
Cascode stages	6 2-way	9 4-way	14 4-way	20 4-way	8 2-way
Gain (dB)	22.5	25	12.5	16.4	18.4
PAE _{max} (%)	2.96	0.5	1	3.13	2.1
P_{sat} (dBm)	9.5	9.6	12	14.7	8.5
P_{sat} BW _{3dB} (GHz)	38	34*	50*	45*	70
P_{sat} BW _{3dB} (%)	17.3	15.8	21.7	20.5	31.8
P_{DC} (mW)	245	1824	740	940.5	327.8
f_{max} (GHz)	500	370	500	450	450
Scalability	no	no	no	no	yes

* Graphical estimation.

The large BW of the stage is realized by inductive gain peaking. The overall gain and P_{sat} over BW are scalable according to the system requirements without manipulating delicate MNs due to the proposed approach. To prove the concept, a PA prototype is implemented in SiGe BiCMOS with eight common broadband amplification stages to have a measured small-signal peak gain of 27.6 dB from 140 to 238.7 GHz, peak P_{sat} of 8.5-dBm, PAE_{max} of 2.1%, and 3-dB P_{sat} BW of 31.8%.

REFERENCES

- [1] Q. Meng et al., "A 200GHz power amplifier with 15.3-dBm P_{sat} utilizing Gm-boosting and multi-coupled-line balun combining in 130-nm SiGe BiCMOS," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Wireless Symp. (IWS)*, May 2025, pp. 1–3.
- [2] A. Ali, P. Colantonio, F. Giannini, D. Kissinger, H. J. Ng, and J. Yun, "A 18-dBm G-band power amplifier using 130-nm SiGe BiCMOS technology," in *Proc. 14th Eur. Microw. Integr. Circuits Conf. (EuMIC)*, Sep. 2019, pp. 164–167.
- [3] L. Guo, S. Li, W. Chen, S. Ma, and J. Ren, "A 140- and 220-GHz dual-band amplifier in 130-nm SiGe BiCMOS process," *IEEE Trans. THz Sci. Technol.*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 768–773, Sep. 2024.
- [4] D. Park, B. Yun, D. Utomo, J. Hong, and S. Lee, "A 201- and 283-GHz dual-band amplifier in 65-Nm CMOS adopting dual-frequency G_{max} -core with dual-band matching," *IEEE Trans. THz Sci. Technol.*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 221–230, May 2023.
- [5] A. Karakuzulu, M. Eissa, D. Kissinger, and A. Malignaggi, "A broadband 110–170-GHz stagger-tuned power amplifier with 13.5-dBm P_{sat} in 130-nm SiGe," *IEEE Microw. Wireless Technol. Lett.*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 56–59, Jan. 2021.
- [6] X. Zhang, Z. Liu, and F. Meng, "A 203-to-250 GHz staggered-tuning amplifier in 0.13- μm SiGe technology," *IEEE Microw. Wireless Technol. Lett.*, vol. 35, no. 7, pp. 1049–1052, Jul. 2025.
- [7] X. Chen, J. Winkelhake, M. Wei, and R. Negra, "15-40 GHz broadband variable gain amplifier with 24.5 dB linear-in-decibel gain control range in SiGe BiCMOS," in *Proc. Int. Symp. Circuits Syst. (ISCAS)*, May 2025, pp. 1–4.
- [8] M. Ohtomo, "Stability analysis and numerical simulation of multidevice amplifiers," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 41, no. 6, pp. 983–991, Jul. 1993.
- [9] J. Cheron et al., "Improving on-wafer characterization of sub-THz devices: A probe influence and crosstalk study," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 73, no. 6, pp. 3144–3155, Jun. 2025.
- [10] Z. Li et al., "A 220-GHz power amplifier with 22.5-dB Gain and 9-dBm P_{sat} in 130-nm SiGe," *IEEE Microw. Wireless Technol. Lett.*, vol. 31, no. 10, pp. 1166–1169, Oct. 2021.
- [11] N. Sarmah, K. Aufinger, R. Lachner, and U. Pfeiffer, "A 200–225 GHz SiGe power amplifier with peak P_{sat} of 9.6 dBm using wideband power combination," in *Proc. 42nd Eur. Solid-State Circuits Conf.*, Sep. 2016, pp. 193–196.
- [12] M. Eissa and D. Kissinger, "A 13.5dBm fully integrated 200-to-255GHz power amplifier with a 4-way power combiner in SiGe: C BiCMOS," in *IEEE Int. Solid-State Circuits Conf. (ISSCC) Dig. Tech. Papers*, Feb. 2019, pp. 82–84.
- [13] J. Yu et al., "A 211-to-263-GHz dual-LC-tank-based broadband power amplifier with 14.7-dBm P_{SAT} and 16.4-dB peak gain in 130-nm SiGe BiCMOS," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 58, no. 2, pp. 332–344, Feb. 2023.